

Abstract**Bacterial Isolates from Infected Wounds and their Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern from Bauchi State**

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Background: Managing wound infections is a challenging task. Wound infection plays an important role in the development of chronicity and delays wound healing. Understanding the resistance patterns of the isolates is an essential step in reducing their burden in hospital settings. The study aimed to determine the bacteriological profile of wound infections and the antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of the most common isolates in the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare.

Materials and Methods: The study retrospectively analysed the antibiograms of wound infections from patients attending

Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare, for over 2 years (2023-2025). Data were collected and cleaned in Excel, and SPSS was used for analysis.

Results: A total of 373 non-duplicate wound swab antibiograms were retrieved. The majority of the participants were male, 71.8% (268), and 28.2% (105) were female. About 52.3% (195) and 47.7% (178) of isolates were Gram-negative and Gram-positive, respectively. Predominant pathogens included *Staphylococcus species* 46.1% (172) and *Escherichia coli* 35.5% (131). The antibiogram of the isolates reveals Ceftriaxone 73.4% (274), Gentamicin 58.7% (198), Augmentin 78.1% (291), Imipenem 45% (168), levofloxacin 47.7% (178), Cefpodoxime 45.8% (171), Cefotaxime 43.4% (162), Cefepime 61.4% (229), Erythromycin 59.2% (222) and Septrin 81.2% (303). Multidrug-resistant pathogens account for 61.5% (229) of the isolates.

Conclusions: This study is primarily aimed at health care practitioners who manage wounds, raising awareness of the importance of wound infection and helping them choose appropriate treatment options to control microbial infection in wounds. We recommend conducting a comprehensive study to produce reliable data and address gaps in the diagnosis and management of these infections.

Keywords: wound infection, bacterial isolates, antibiogram

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ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18909907>

Date Submitted: 20th November 2025

Date Accepted: 2nd March 2026

Date Published Online: 10th March 2026

Cite this article as: Abubakar Jibril¹, Jatau Kabir², Mairo Usman Kadaura¹, Hassan Olayinka³, Abdulaziz Abubakar Abdullahi⁴, Abdul Baba Zamo⁴. Bacterial Isolates from Infected Wounds and their Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern from Bauchi State *The Scholar J Health Scie* 2026; S2- 5